

THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES FROM REACTIVE RESIN SYSTEMS – CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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1. Introduction

Fiber-reinforced plastics are composite materials consisting of polymer matrix and fiber reinforcement. Common fibers used for composite materials include glass, carbon and other inorganic fibers. The reinforcement of polymer matrix with fibers enhances the mechanical properties such as tensile strength and stiffness; and renders the final composite product useful in applications where a lightweight high-strength material is required.

The polymer matrix of composite materials can be thermoplastic or thermoset resins, depending on the requirements of specific applications. Thermoset resins consist of low molecular weight monomers or oligomers. Typically thermoset resin starts as a low viscosity liquid, which enables fast resin impregnation of reinforcing fibers. After resin impregnation, thermoset resin can be cured to form cross-linked structure, changing its state from a liquid to a solid. However, once cured thermoset resins are not thermoformable; and the resulting composite materials are not recyclable. Due to the crosslinked structure of resin matrix, thermoset composites typically lack impact resistance. In addition, thermoset resins and their intermediate materials, such as pre-pregs, have limited shelf life.

On the other hand, thermoplastic resins are recyclable and thermoformable. Compared with their thermoset counterparts, thermoplastic resins have superior properties such as high toughness and impact resistance. Due to these unique properties, thermoplastic composites are

gaining more interest over the past decades. In addition, thermoplastic resins and their intermediates (pre-pregs, consolidated laminates such as organo-sheets) have unlimited shelf life. Traditionally thermoplastic composite materials have been manufactured by melt processing processes, such as pre-pregging and compression molding.

Despite the fact that thermoplastic composites have the above-mentioned advantages over their thermoset counterparts, so far their applications have been limited, especially in structural applications where large continuous fiber reinforced composite parts are needed, due to the following drawbacks:

- (1) The very high melt viscosity of thermoplastic polymers significantly slows down resin impregnation and fiber wet-out; therefore the achievable part size and thickness of thermoplastic composites are limited.
- (2) Currently, continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics typically requires the use of intermediate materials such as pre-pregs or organo-sheets, which adds to the material costs significantly.
- (3) The fiber-to-matrix interface of thermoplastic composites produced from melt processing is often low, because of the significantly lower reactivity of thermoplastic polymers than the monomeric/oligomeric precursors for thermosets.
- (4) Tooling and equipment costs for the melt processing of thermoplastic resins are typically very high, due to the need of high pressure and high temperature.

To overcome the high melt viscosity of thermoplastic resins and make them suitable for

liquid molding processes, reactive thermoplastic resins have been developed for thermoplastic composites. Reactive resin systems, such as the anionic ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam to form polyamide-6, overcome the limitations of traditional thermoplastic resins by starting with low-viscosity monomers or oligomers, very much like thermoset resins. Therefore reactive thermoplastic resin combines the best of the two resin systems – the process advantages of thermoset resin and the property advantages of thermoplastic resin.

For example, caprolactam has a melt viscosity that is orders of magnitude lower than typical polyamide-6 melt. The water-like caprolactam melt allows rapid resin impregnation and complete fiber wet-out without the need for high temperature and high pressure. The subsequent in-situ polymerization of caprolactam, in the presence of reinforcing fibers, forms high molecular weight polyamide-6. Unlike the conventional thermoplastic polymer melt process, the extremely low viscosity of caprolactam allows the use of structural molding process, such as resin transfer molding (RTM), with continuous fiber reinforcement to produce structural composite part. Excellent resin impregnation of continuous fiber reinforcement, such as glass fiber woven fabric, by caprolactam melt can be achieved within significantly reduced impregnation time.

In addition, the reactive thermoplastic resin systems require significantly lower processing temperatures, as compared to the corresponding polymer melt processing systems. Therefore the tooling cost and energy usage will be reduced. These reactive resin systems enable the efficient production of thermoplastic composites with the processing techniques traditionally designed for low-viscosity thermoset resins.

In this research, reactive resin transfer molding of caprolactam was used to prepare high-performance continuous glass fiber reinforced polyamide-6 composites suitable for structural applications. Mechanical testing of the resulting composite panels demonstrated that the

continuous fiber reinforced polyamide-6 based composites have comparable mechanical strengths to epoxy- and polyurethane-based thermoset composites, and superior toughness and impact resistance. In addition, by coupling ring-opening polymerization activator to glass fibers, the bonding between glass fiber and polyamide-6 matrix was enhanced, resulting in significant improvement in mechanical properties of the composite materials.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of unidirectional stitched glass fiber fabric reinforcement

1,200 tex fiber glass rovings were weaved to a unidirectional stitched fabric with the area weight of 670 g/m². Six layers of the unidirectional fabric were stacked in an alternate 0/90° layup; and the 6-layer stack was then cut to 400 mm×400 mm and placed into a mold as reinforcement for the preparation of the composite panel via resin transfer molding, as described in Section 2.2.

2.2. Resin transfer molding and in-situ ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam

Two heated tanks were used for melting caprolactam-catalyst and caprolactam-activator mixtures separately. Into the first tank, 1,000 grams of caprolactam (Brüggemann, AP Nylon grade) and 82.4 grams of Bruggolen C10 (Brüggemann, contains 17-19% sodium caprolactamate) were added and the mixture was melted at 110°C. Separately, 1,000 grams of caprolactam (Brüggemann, AP Nylon grade) and 27.0 grams of Bruggolen C20 (Brüggemann, contains 80% caprolactam hexane di-isocyanate) were added to the second tank; and the mixture was melted at 110°C.

The melts from the two tanks were then mixed at a 1:1 ratio in a static mixer, before the reactive mixture was injected into the mold. The reactive mixture in this example contains 0.6 mol% of active catalyst (sodium

caprolactamate) and 0.3 mol% of active activator (caprolactam hexane di-isocyanate).

After the reactive mixture was injected into the mold, the mold temperature was raised to 160°C to polymerize caprolactam in situ in the presence of glass fabric reinforcement. The resulting composite panels have a glass content of 70% by weight.

2.3. Test methods

2.3.1. Tensile strength

Tensile strength of the composite samples was tested based on ISO 527-3 standard (Type 2 sample). A gauge length of 150 mm and a testing speed of 2 mm/min were used for testing. For each composite panel, eight samples of 250 mm in length and 25 mm in width were cut for tensile tests.

2.3.2. Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS)

ILSS tests were conducted based on ASTM 2344 standard. A span length of 12 mm and a testing speed of 1 mm/min were used for testing. For each composite panel, 10 samples of 40 mm in length and 6 mm in width were cut for ILSS tests.

2.3.3. Flexural strength

Flexural strength tests were conducted based on ISO 178 standard. A span length of 48 mm and a testing speed of 1 mm/min were used for

testing. For each composite panel, 10 samples of 60 mm in length and 25 mm in width were cut for flexural strength tests.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Anionic polymerization of caprolactam

Among reactive thermoplastic resin systems, one of the most studied is the anionic ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam to produce polyamide-6. Ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam requires a catalyst and an activator in addition to caprolactam monomer. Typical caprolactam resin system used for molding processes consists of two components, i.e. a monomer-catalyst mixture and a monomer-activator mixture, respectively. The two mixtures are melted in two separate tanks and then mixed together in a mixing chamber prior to resin injection. Figure 1 shows the reaction scheme of ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam using sodium caprolactam as the catalyst and acylcaprolactam as the activator.

Caprolactam has a melting temperature of 69°C and a melt viscosity of 3.6 mPa·s at 110°C. Because of its water-like viscosity, caprolactam can be used in various structural molding processes, such as resin transfer molding, structural reaction injection molding (SRIM),

Fig. 1. Anionic ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam.

and vacuum infusion.

Due to the nature of anionic polymerization, ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam is very sensitive to proton-donating agents or oxygen. Proton-donating agents, such as water, acids and alcohols, have to be removed from the polymerization system; otherwise they will deactivate the highly reactive anionic species in the polymerization mixture, causing termination or incomplete polymerization. All the polymerization ingredients and the reinforcing fibers have to be as moisture-free as possible to ensure high monomer conversion. Fortunately, in a closed molding system, such as RTM, dry reinforcing fibers and polymerization ingredients can be kept under a nitrogen-protected environment to prevent moisture uptake from the ambient, without adding significant cost to the process. It has been demonstrated in our RTM experiments that a high monomer conversion (>97%) can be achieved by pre-drying reinforcing fiber glass fabric and using polymerization ingredients of very low moisture content, such as caprolactam of AP Nylon grade.

Additionally, the sizing chemistry for fibers has to be designed to be compatible with the polymerization system. Any proton-donating materials in the sizing formulation will deactivate anionic catalyst, causing incomplete polymerization and weak fiber-resin interphase. Therefore, proton-donating ingredients need to be avoided or minimized in the sizing formulation designed for reactive caprolactam resin system.

3.2 Polyamide-6 composite from reactive resin transfer molding

High-performance continuous glass fiber reinforced polyamide-6 composites suitable for structural applications have been produced using processing techniques such as reactive resin transfer molding. It has been demonstrated that the continuous fiber reinforced polyamide-6 based composites have comparable mechanical strengths to epoxy- and polyurethane-based

thermoset composites, and superior toughness and impact resistance. These thermoplastic composites can be thermal-formed, welded and recycled. Potential applications include highly loaded structural automotive parts.

Figure 2 shows a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrograph of stitched fabric used in this study. As can be seen in the micrograph, bundles of glass fibers are tied closely by stitches in the stitched fabric. Therefore it is very critical to have a resin system with very low viscosity so that the complete resin impregnation and fiber wet-out can be achieved in a short period of time. For example, the complete resin impregnation of the 6-layer stack of stitched glass fabric used in this study can be achieved with the water-like caprolactam melt within seconds.

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph of stitched unidirectional glass fabric used in this study.

After the completion of resin impregnation, the mold temperature was raised to the polymerization temperature of caprolactam, for example 160°C, to form polyamide-6 in-situ. Figure 3 shows a SEM micrograph of the cross-section of polyamide-6/glass fiber composite. In this back-scattered electron microscopy image, the bright areas are the fiber reinforcement, and the grey areas are the polyamide-6 matrix. One can clearly see the six layers of stitched unidirectional glass fabric in an alternate 0/90°

layup fashion. The rovings perpendicular to the cross-section plane shows as the ellipse shape. The completed resin impregnation can be seen throughout the entire thickness of composite panel. A closer look of the cross-section of the roving in the composite indicated the complete fiber wet-out, as shown in Figure 4. These SEM micrographs clearly demonstrated the advantages of low-viscosity reactive thermoplastic resins in resin impregnation and fiber wet-out, which is unmatched by the conventional melt processing of thermoplastic polymers.

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of the cross-section of the composite panel consisting of polyamide-6 matrix and a 6-layer 0/90° stack of stitched glass fiber fabric.

Fig. 4. High-magnification SEM micrograph showing the complete fiber wet-out in the polyamide-6 composite.

As expected, the resulting continuous fiber-reinforced polyamide-6 composites have superior impact resistance. Figure 5 shows a digital photograph of the impact zone of the polyamide-6 composite panel from the falling dart impact test (using the hemispherical impact tip of 0.5 inch in diameter). The impact tests showed the damage by the falling dart was confined in the area where the dart hit; and no apparent damage was observed in the area outside of the impact zone.

Fig. 5. Photograph of the impact zone (back side) of polyamide-6/glass fabric composite panel from the falling dart impact test.

Fig. 6. Photograph of the impact zone (back side) of epoxy/glass fabric composite panel from the falling dart impact test. Epoxy resin: Huntsman Epoxy 3585 with XB 3458 hardener (100/19).

On the other hand, composites with thermoset matrix resins, such as epoxy, are brittle and therefore are less impact-resistant. As shown in Figure 6, the impact tests of an epoxy composite panel reinforced with the same glass fabric showed that the damage propagated outward from the impact zone. The degree of damage is significantly higher for epoxy composites than that for polyamide-6 composites, due to the brittleness of thermoset resins.

3.3 Reactive fiber glass

In the field of glass fiber-reinforced polymer composite, it is well known that the interfacial strength between fiber and polymer matrix plays a critical role in the mechanical performance of composite material. If there is a strong interfacial bonding between glass fibers and resin matrix, the stress can be transmitted from the matrix phase to glass fibers, thereby maximizing the overall composite strength. If the bonding between the matrix phase and the reinforcing fibers is too weak to transmit the stress, then reinforcing fibers can slip out of the matrix and the strength of the fibers will not be transmitted to the matrix.

Unfortunately for thermoplastic composites produced by conventional polymer melt processing techniques, the potential in the composite mechanical properties has not always been fully realized, due largely to the poor fiber-to-matrix interface. For example, the fatigue performance of thermoplastic composites is often disappointingly low, despite the high toughness of thermoplastic matrix resin [1]. Fatigue resistance is critical for applications where the composite parts are subject to high-frequency cyclic loadings. As an example, wind turbine blade is subjected to a total of 10^9 cyclic loadings during its entire lifetime, which renders the fatigue resistance one of the most critical properties.

In order to improve the interfacial adhesion between glass fibers and polymer matrix, glass

fibers are typically treated with a sizing composition after they are drawn from bushing. Typically this is achieved by using silane coupling agent in the sizing for glass fiber. The functional groups on the silane coupling agent add to the adhesion through physical and/or covalent bonding. Covalent bonding is preferred, as it is much stronger and more durable than physical bonding. Covalent bonding not only improves the mechanical properties but also the aging performance of composite materials.

For thermoplastic polymers such as polyamides, the challenge in promoting adhesion through silane coupling agents is far greater than thermosets which start with monomeric or oligomeric precursors of higher reactivity. For conventional thermoplastic composites, the silane coupling agents on reinforcing fibers must react with the polymer but not the monomeric/oligomeric precursors. The low reactivity of many thermoplastic polymers significantly limits the avenues for coupling reaction.

For reactive thermoplastic resins systems, however, silane coupling agents can be chosen such that they can react with monomers/oligomers, similar to the case of thermoset resins. For example, for the ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam, a silane coupling agent possessing a polymerization activator group can be used to covalently bond activator functionality to glass fiber. The bonded activator renders the glass fibers reactive and enables the grafting of polyamide-6 chains directly from glass fibers; therefore the interfacial strength between glass fiber and polyamide-6 resin matrix is greatly enhanced.

The coupling silane-activator can be represented as shown in formula 1:

wherein S represents a silane coupling moiety capable of bonding to the surface of glass fiber; A represents a ring-opening polymerization activator moiety; and X represents a linking

moiety capable of linking the S moiety and the A moiety. A may be an N-substituted imide group that serves as the activator in the anionic ring-opening polymerization of lactams. Such polymerization is well known in literature [2-5]. One example of the coupling activator for ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam is 2-oxo-N-(3-triethoxysilyl)-propyl-azepane-1-carboxamide [6].

The reactive glass, which contain surface-bonded activator moiety, can be placed in a mold in the form of woven or nonwoven fabrics, nonwoven mats, rovings, etc. The subsequent in-situ ring-opening polymerization of lactam monomers from glass surface forms polyamide chains with one chain end covalently bonded to glass surface.

Figures 7-8 show typical SEM micrographs of polyamide-6 based composites reinforced by a commercial non-reactive glass (Figure 7) and a reactive glass treated with a coupling activator, 2-oxo-N-(3-triethoxysilyl)propyl)azepane-1-carboxamide (Figure 8). In the case of glass fiber treated with a sizing containing no silane-activator, the poor resin-glass interface leads to failure at the fiber-resin interface (Figure 7). While for the glass fiber treated with a silane-activator, high degree of resin-glass bonding was achieved and the failure in the composite occurs within the resin matrix (Figure 8).

By covalently bonding thermoplastic resins to glass fibers through the coupling silane-activator, the mechanical properties of polyamide-6 composites are improved significantly, as shown in Figure 9. Compared with the composite reinforced with non-reactive glass, the interlaminar shear strength, flexural strength, and tensile strength were improved by using a reactive glass possessing surface-bonded activator.

Fig. 7. SEM image of the polyamide-6 based composite reinforced by fiber glass coated with a sizing containing no coupling activator.

Fig. 8. SEM image of the polyamide-6 based composite reinforced by fiber glass coated with a reactive sizing containing a coupling activator.

Fig. 9. Improvements in mechanical properties of polyamide-6 composites reinforced with reactive glass vs. non-reactive glass.

4. Summary

Fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites are gaining increasing interest due to their superior impact resistance, weldability and recyclability. However, due to the high melt viscosity of thermoplastic resins, conventional melting processing techniques for thermoplastic composites have significant limitations in part size and thickness, and are not suitable for structural molding process.

Reactive thermoplastic resins, which start with monomers or low molecular weight oligomers, overcome the viscosity issue of the conventional thermoplastic resin systems. Anionic ring-opening polymerization of caprolactam, for example, starts with water-like caprolactam melt, can be used in structural molding process traditionally designed for thermoset resins. High performance continuous glass fiber reinforced polyamide-6 composites can be produced through reactive resin transfer molding.

Furthermore, by covalently bonding ring-opening polymerization activator to glass fibers, the interfacial strength between polyamide-6 matrix and glass fibers can be greatly enhanced; resulting in significant improvement in mechanical strengths of composite materials.

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